

Relation between Lattice Energy and Melting Points of Some Crystalline Substances. Part VIII

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Utilising the absolute critical temperature (T_c) data for solids of high melting points, as recorded by von Grosse, it has been shown that the absolute melting points (T_m) of alkali halides and of alkali and some other metals are the corresponding temperatures. T_m , T_b (absolute boiling point), and T_c of francium halides and alkali astatides have been estimated from the known approximate constant ratios: $-U_0/T_m$, $-U_0/T_b$, and $-U_0/T_c$ ($-U_0$ being the lattice energy) for the other members of this family. Further, T_m 's of KcF_3 and KcF_4 are estimated to be about 100° and 190° , respectively, and the heat of sublimation of KcF_3 to be about 10.4 kcal.

The approximate constancy of the ratios T_m/T_c or T_b/T_c for sets of simple and similar atomic and molecular solids of low melting and boiling points is usually believed to show that T_m 's and T_b 's are the corresponding temperatures. The same procedure could not be employed for the substances of high T_m because no reliable values of T_c for this class of substances have been available. Hence it is usually believed that T_m 's and T_b 's in such cases have no particular theoretical significance although attempts have been made to correlate them with some physical properties of the substances concerned to show that T_m 's (and T_b 's) are the corresponding temperatures for similar systems^{1,2}. The earlier data on critical temperatures of such solids, obtained by Guldberg³ and others⁴, have been discredited as these were found to be low. Von Grosse *et al.*⁵ have obtained the critical temperatures of some salts and metals⁶. This offers an opportunity to examine the corresponding nature of the absolute melting points in heavier solids and to see how far the earlier conclusions, based on the indirect method, namely, $-U_0/T_m = \text{constant}$, are in conformity with those of the conventional critical temperature method. In the present communication the data of von Grosse *et al.*⁵ on T_c 's of alkali halides and metals have been used to verify the conclusions of the indirect method in some heavier solids like salts and metals.

The ratios T_m/T_c and $-U_0/T_c$ for alkali halides have been calculated and are recorded in Table I.

1. Gopal, this *Journal*, 1953, 29, 55 and later communications in the same series.
2. Partington, "An Advanced Treatise on Physical Chemistry", Vol. III, Longmans and Green & Co., London, 1952, p.552.
3. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1887, 1, 234.
4. Von Grosse, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, 24, 446 and other papers of the series.
5. *Ibid.*, 1961, 22, 28; 1962, 24, 353; 1963, 25, 331; *Science*, 1963, 140, 381.

* The values of T_c have been obtained assuming similarity between these and mercury, which may not be justified. For example, Walling and Lemmon (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, 68, 534) believe that for the alkali metals, T_c 's obtained by von Grosse, using mercury as reference fluid and assuming the law of corresponding states, contain systematic errors. However, these values of T_c 's are claimed to have been verified^{4,5} by an independent method, based on the law of rectilinear diameters.

TABLE I

 T_m/T_0 and $-U_0/T_0$ ratios.

	$-U_0$ (kcal.)	T_m (°K)	T_0 (°K)	T_m/T_0	$-U_0/T_0$ (cal./deg.)		$-U_0$ (kcal.)	T_m (°K)	T_0 (°K)	$-T_m/T_0$	$-U_0/T_0$ (cal./deg.)
A. Alkali halides.											
LiF	240	1143	4140	0.28	58	LiCl	109	886	3080	0.29	54
LiBr	188	820	3020	0.27	63	LiI	174	719	3250	0.22	54
NaF	213	1253	5270	0.29	50	NaCl	183	1077	3400	0.32	54
NaBr	175	1028	3200	0.32	55	NaI	164	924	3160	0.32	52
KF	190	1153	3460	0.34	55	KCl	165	1048	3200	0.33	52
KBr	159	1003	3170	0.32	51	KI	151	996	2960	0.33	53
RbF	162	1033	3280	0.32	55	RbCl	160	988	3140	0.32	51
RbBr	150	967	3130	0.31	49	RbI	145	913	3055	0.30	48
CsF	174	956	2915	0.33	60	CsCl	152	919	3040	0.31	50
CsBr	146	909	3045	0.31	48	CsI	139	894	3020	0.30	46
B. Alkali and alkaline earth metals.											
Li	175	453	3480	0.13	50	Na	148	371	2800	0.13	52
K	128	335	2440	0.14	52	Rb	120	312	2190	0.14	54
Cs	113	302	2150	0.14	52						
Ca	456	1083	7200	0.15	63	Sr	427	1073	7100	0.15	58
Ba	413	1123	7400	0.15	55						
Ag	..	1024	7500	0.14	..	Fe	..	1808	10000	0.18	..
Ni	..	1728	10700	0.16	..	Mo	..	2823	17000	0.19	..
Ta	..	3073	22000	0.14	..	Re	..	3410	20500	0.17	..
W	..	3543	23000	0.16	..						

DISCUSSION

It may be observed from Table Ia that T_m/T_0 is approximately constant (ca. 0.3) for all the salts and so their T_m 's are the corresponding temperatures, thus supporting the conclusions, obtained earlier, from the relation $-U_0/T_m = \text{constant}$. It may be noted that $-U_0/T_0$ is constant as well as its value for different halides is about 53 cal./deg. It may be seen from Table Ib that for the alkali and some alkaline earth metals $-U_0/T_0$ is about 52 cal./deg. For other metals, T_0 values have not been estimated although $-U_0$ values have been obtained of doubtful accuracy⁶.

The values of $-U_0/T_0$ and T_m/T_0 for alkali and alkaline earth metals are recorded in Table Ib which also includes similar data for some transition metals for which T_0 values have been reported⁵.

It is clear from Table Ib that for alkali and alkaline earth metals $T_m/T_0 \approx 0.14$ and for transition metals it is 0.17, from which and other similar relations one can make a good guess about T_0 's of other similar transition metals.

The constancy of the relations T_m/T_0 , T_b/T_0 , $-U_0/T_0$, etc. is no doubt due to the fact that the law of corresponding states is, at least approximately, applicable to sets of similar substances even of high melting and boiling points like common inorganic salts and metals. Naturally it follows that T_m 's and T_b 's for similar systems are the corresponding temperatures and so T_m/T_0 and T_b/T_0 are simply the reduced temperatures. Although attempts have been made earlier⁷ to explain, at least qualitatively, these results, it will be appropriate to provide a more rigorous and quantitative explanation. Pitzer's theory of the corresponding states⁷, based on the dimensional analysis of the configurational integral:

$$Z = \int \dots \int_V \exp(-W/RT) dv_0 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

has been extended, making some reasonable approximations, to inorganic salts by Reiss *et al.*⁸ The essence of the theory is that the corresponding states concept will be applicable to systems governed by the same force laws and the pair potential ought to possess no more than a single distance parameter. If U_{ij} represents the potential energy between two molecules or ions 'i' and 'j', then for uni-univalent salts, one can write:

$$U_{ij} = -\frac{(Ze)^2}{k\epsilon r_{ij}} \quad \text{if } r_{ij} \gg \lambda \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where r_{ij} is the distance of separation, λ being its value at equilibrium, and k is the dielectric constant. So that for equilibrium, equation (1) can be written as

$$U_{ij} = -\frac{(Ze)^2}{k\lambda} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

It has been further shown that

$$\frac{k\lambda T_m}{Z^2} = T_m = \text{constant}$$

for similar systems as defined above. Substituting the value of λ in equation (3), one gets

$$U_{ij} = -\frac{(Ze)^2 T_m}{kZ^2 T_m} = \frac{-e^2 T_m}{T_m}$$

or

$$\frac{U_{ij}}{T_m} = \frac{-e^2}{T_m} = \text{constant.}$$

Now the pair potential U_{ij} on suitable summation should provide the lattice energy $-U_0$ so that $-U_0/T_m = \text{constant}$. Similar arguments can be advanced to other similar salt systems. Although in metals the force law may not be very simple, it is plausible to assume that it will also contain one distance parameter and so the same line of arguments may be applicable to similar metals also.

Some Applications of the Relations $-U_0/T_0 = \text{Constant}$ and $-U_0/T_m = \text{Constant}$

It appears now established that these relations hold good for sets of simple and similar substances. Hence one can venture to use them to estimate T_m , T_b , T_0 , and $-U_0$ from the available data in appropriate cases.

7. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, 7, 583.

8. *Ibid.*, 1961, 35, 820.

An application of these relations is to calculate $-U_0$ of a solid from the knowledge of T_m , T_b , or T_0 and *vice versa*, provided that one can assign the family of the solid so that the value of the appropriate ratio is known. One such application has been pointed out⁹ in solid radon which is a noble gas. From its T_m (202° K), the value of $-U_0$ was estimated to be 4850 cal./mole. A better approximation, 4950 cal., leads to 291° K for the value of ϵ/k of the L-J potential function for radon, which agrees excellently with 290° K, obtained by Miller¹⁰ from a different procedure. Similarly, T_0 of radon could be estimated to be 367° K ($-U_0/T_0$ for inert gases is about 13.3), the literature value being 377.6° K. Similar other cases of present day interest may be examined. For example, one may try to calculate the melting points of XeF_2 and XeF_4 and $-U_0$ for XeF_6 . For the simple molecular gases, to which class xenon fluorides should belong, $-U_0/T_m$ is about 33. Heats of sublimation of XeF_2 and XeF_4 are 12.3 and 15.3 kcal., respectively¹¹. Hence their respective approximate melting points should be 100° and 100°. Again from the T_m of XeF_6 as 319° K (45°)¹², its heat of sublimation should be 10.4 kcal., which is lower than that of either XeF_2 and XeF_4 , as was expected by Jortner *et al.*¹¹.

Similarly, one can estimate T_m , T_b , and T_0 of the less-common alkali halides like FrF , FrCl , FrBr , FrI , FrAt , LiAt , NaAt , KAt , RbAt , and CsAt from the lattice energies of these salts, estimated by Ladd and Lee¹³. From the approximate known ratios $-U_0/T_m$, $-U_0/T_b$, and $-U_0/T_0$, the T_m , T_b , and T_0 of francium halides and alkali astatides have been estimated and are shown in Table II.

TABLE II
T_m, T_b, and T₀ of francium halides and alkali astatides

	FrF.	FrCl.	FrBr.	FrI.	FrAt.	LiAt.	NaAt.	KAt.	RbAt.	CsAt.
$-U_0$ (kcal.)..	171	151	146	139	137	172	157	147	142	140
T_m (°K)..	950	916	912	891	877	717	624	680	687	675
($-U_0/T_m=0.16$) [*]										
T_b (°K)—	1700	1690	1670	1544	1520	1600	1670	1610	1578	1556
($-U_0/T_b=0.09$) [*]										
T_0 (°K)—	3420	3020	2900	2780	2740	3440	3140	2940	2840	2800
($-U_0/T_0=0.05$) [*]										

*See ref. 1: The values of $-U_0/T_m$ and $-U_0/T_b$ for alkali halides fluctuate and vary slightly from salt to salt. For lithium salts the values are usually higher. The most appropriate value of the constant has been used taking into consideration the closer similarity of the salts given in Table III with other alkali halides. The value of $-U_0/T_m$ and $-U_0/T_b$, quoted here, are only approximate average values.

More examples can be cited, illustrating the utility of these functions in the domain of substances of both high and low melting points. It is obvious that these could be used in a wide field in appropriate cases and should be ranked with Trouton's rule. Their limitations are obvious and one should be on guard while making use of them.

CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY,
LUCKNOW.

Received August 17, 1964.

9. Gopal, this *Journal*, 1962, **29**, 791.
10. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1960, **64**, 163.
11. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 814.
12. Malm *et al.*, *ibid.*, p. 110.
13. *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 164.